

The Role of Social Identity Labels in VEs on User Behavior

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Questionnaire

Comments for easier navigation in this document are in italics and were not displayed in the actual questionnaire.

Pre-Experimental Section: Instructions and Overview

Section 1

Subject of the study

The subject of the current study is the collaboration of groups in VR.

Structure

The experiment is divided into 5 parts:

First, you will be given some information about the technology in use and instructions on how to put it on, and on the experiment. Further, you will be asked to fill out section 1 of the survey with the tablet. Your current section is displayed at the top of every page.

Then you need to put the headset (HMD) on and wait for the experimenter and the other player. The experimenter will introduce you via voicechat.

Subsequently, you will be asked to answer section 2 of the questionnaire using the tablet. When you have finished, please put the HMD on again and wait for the experimenter.

Then the actual experiment starts including multiple stages of a trading game and a puzzle game. You will communicate via voice chat with your other team player. You are supposed to act as you would under normal circumstances in order to generate authentic data. Do not try to please the experimenter.

After the experimental trial, you are asked to resume section 3 of the questionnaire. It asks about your experience in VR. You will be informed by the experimenter when to resume the questionnaire. After you completed section 3 of the questionnaire, the experiment is over.

Please try to answer every question completely. Simply start on the first page and answer every question one after another. You cannot fail or make mistakes as the questionnaire is about your individual opinion and assessment. Only the test environment will be evaluated, neither you personally nor your individual behavior. If there are specific instructions for a questionnaire section, they are explained at the beginning of the section. If you have any questions, feel free to ask at any time. Indicate that you have a question either by talking to the experimenter or by raising your hand. Only the experimenter will hear your question.

Please note: It is of utmost importance that you do not reveal any personal information during the experiment (e.g., state your name, age, where you are from, your study courses..)!

Thank you very much for your participation!

Best Regards,

Instructions and Technology in Use

Technology in Use

You will be using two devices for this experiment: The Oculus Rift VR Headset and this tablet. The tablet is only for filling out the questionnaire. You will be told at specific points when to stop or to resume the questionnaire and when to put on the VR Headset again. When you have finished a section of the questionnaire, simply put it on the table and continue using the lower button when you are asked to.

Fitting

You can adjust the headset using the straps on the sides and on the top to your head. If your vision is unclear, adjust the distance of the lenses by pushing in the lever on the bottom side of the headset and move it to the right or left.

The VR Headset serves 2 purposes: 1. for the VR experience, 2. to communicate with your team player and the experimenter. During the whole experience, you are member of 2 video conferences: one is only for you and the experimenter. A webcam is filming you so that in case you have a question or there occur any hard- or software issues, or you have a question you can always talk to the experimenter. **The microphone and audio of the VR Headset is used which means that if you do not wear the headset, you cannot hear the experimenter or your team player.** Thus, to signalize that you are in need of help, simply raise your hand and the experimenter will unmute you. No video or audio footage will be collected.

The second video conference is to communicate with your team player and the experimenter. The experimenter will mute and unmute you remotely. You do not have to set up anything.

Input Controllers

For the experiment, you will be using the Oculus controllers. There is one for your left and one for your right hand. There are four trigger buttons or thumb sticks that are important: the Hand Triggers and the thumb sticks on each controller (see figure below).

The thumb stick on the left controller is used to move around. Push the thumb stick forward to teleport to the end of the line. The thumb stick on the right controller is used to turn around. Push or snap it to the left or right to turn by fixed 15 degrees. Firstly, the Hand Trigger is used to grab objects. To do so, you need to hold your hand in an object and then press the trigger. Then you can move the object. To let it go, simply release the trigger button. Secondly, you use it to press buttons. In one game, you need to enter numbers by pressing buttons, similar to a keyboard. To do so, touch with your pointer the button and then press the trigger button.

Procedure

During the experiment, the experimenter will tell you when to press a yellow button. To indicate that you are ready to start the tasks, one player needs to press the yellow button. Then, the first Daytrader Game Set (see following pages) starts. When this set is finished, the yellow button must be pressed again to start the puzzle game (see following pages). If a puzzle is finished, the yellow button is pressed again to proceed to the next puzzle. Additionally, there is a red button to reset the puzzle tasks if necessary.

Daytrader Game

One part of the experience is the Daytrader Game. In this game you are given tokens that you can invest in either your own individual pool or in a shared corporate pool. Depending on how many tokens you invest, you earn points. There will be 3 sets of the Daytrader Game and every set includes 5 rounds. The goal is to earn as many points as possible. You can invest up to 30 tokens each round. The tokens are reset each round.

Round Nr	
Individual Pool	Points
Corporate Pool	Individual OK <input type="checkbox"/>
Tokens	Corporate OK <input type="checkbox"/>

If you choose to invest in your own individual pool, all your tokens will be doubled at the end of each round so that you have a guaranteed benefit. If you choose to invest in the shared corporate pool of you and your team player, at the end of each set all points will be tripled and then split evenly between both of you. The player with most points will get a bonus of 300 points at the end of a set.

While playing the Daytrader Game, you cannot talk to your team player. However, there will be a discussion round after set 2 so that you can discuss with your team player the strategy for the last set. You will enter a separate room in VR to play the Daytrader Game.

How to enter numbers

You enter the number of tokens by pressing buttons on an interface in VR. To do so, you are given a pointer that you need to touch the buttons with. To enter a number, then press the Hand Trigger Button.

Then choose the numbers you would like to enter. You see the digit you entered on the screen in VR and you hear a sound when you entered a digit. **You need to confirm each number that you entered by pressing the Confirm button (e.g., for the individual pool you enter 10 and then you need to confirm to proceed to the entry for the shared pool).**

If you want to correct your entry, press the Restart button. When you have finished your entry for the round, you need to wait for your team player to finish his/her/their entry before the game continues.

Puzzle Game

You will be playing a puzzle game with your team player. All puzzle pieces are scattered on the yellow floor mat. It is your task to assemble the puzzle on the black floor mat. There are 3 puzzles that you need to solve with varying difficulty. For help, a silhouette of the assembled puzzle is shown to you as a reference, and one piece is already at the correct position. When you grab a piece, it will turn blue. This indicates that you grab this object. When the piece is at the correct position, it will turn green. You need to cooperate and discuss with your team player: **One of you is only able to move the object (i.e., changing its position) while the other one is only able to rotate the object.** Rotation and position of all pieces need to be correct in order to finish the puzzle.

Pre-Experimental Section: Demographics and Sample Description

Your gender

Please enter your gender.

- male
- female
- diverse
- Prefer not to state

Age

Please enter your age.

Do you have a German passport?

If not, please name the country in which your passport was issued.

- Other

How often do you experience VR Content?

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Often
- Daily

How often do you play cooperative games?

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Often
- Daily

You finished section 1 of the questionnaire!

Please stop here. Please notify the experimenter that you have finished with this part. The trial including the introduction in VR will be next. As soon as you get the instruction to resume the questionnaire, please proceed to the tablet again and click on the button at the bottom to continue with section 2 of the questionnaire.

Pre-Interaction (after introduction to team partner): Trust and exploratory Initial Impression questions

Section 2

Trust [6]

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements:

Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I would expect the other person to pay me back if I loaned him/her/them €100							
If the other person laughed unexpectedly at something I did or said, I would know s/he / they was not being unkind							
If the other person gave me a compliment on my haircut, I would believe s/he / they meant what was said							
If the other person borrowed something of value and returned it broken, s/he / they would offer to pay for the repairs							

Initial Impression

Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I could imagine playing for another group							
It is important to me to beat the other teams who participated							
My group has other characteristics that are more important than the goal of this game							

You finished section 2 of the questionnaire!

Please stop here. Please put the HMD on and notify the experimenter that you have finished with this part. The trial including the VR games will be next. As soon as you get the instruction to resume the questionnaire, please proceed to the tablet again and click on the button at the bottom to continue with section 3 of the questionnaire.

Post-Experimental: Group Identification, Trust, Social Presence (CCPiG), Enjoyment, Exploratory Questions, Qualitative Feedback

Section 3

Group Identification [4]

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements:

Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I would prefer to be in a different group							
We like one another in this group							
I enjoy interacting with the other team player in this group							
I don't like the other person in this group							
In this group, we don't have to rely on one another							
Both team players need to contribute to achieve the group's goals							
This group accomplishes things that no single team player could achieve							
In this group, we do not need to cooperate to complete group tasks							
I think of this group as part of who I am							
I see myself as quite different from the other team player in this group							

I don't think of this group as part of who I am							
I see myself as quite similar to the other team player in this group							

Trust [6]

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements:

Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I would expect the other person to pay me back if I loaned him/her/them €100							
If the other person laughed unexpectedly at something I did or said, I would know s/he / they was not being unkind							
If the other person gave me a compliment on my haircut, I would believe s/he / they meant what was said							
If the other person borrowed something of value and returned it broken, s/he / they would							

offer to pay for the repairs							
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Social Presence (CCPiG by [5])

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements:

Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
It was as much about the team as about my own game							
I felt my team shared a common overall aim							
I felt my teammate was looking out for me							
I felt my team was committed to working together							
Being part of a team motivated me							
My team communicated well							
The team had a mutual understanding							
I put the performance of the team over my personal performance							
My teammate played a significant role in my game experience							
I felt a social connection to my teammate							
I felt like I was part of a team							

I felt my team shared common short-term goals							
My teammate was useful							
I felt the team helped me							
I acted with my teammate in mind							
I considered my teammate's possible plans/thoughts							
I did not want my teammate to think I had let him/her / them down							
I felt I contributed to the team							
I felt my actions made a difference to my teammate							
My actions were determined by the objectives of the team							
The actions of my teammate affected my thoughts and actions							
I wanted my teammate to value me							
I felt responsible for achieving the objectives of the team							
I made an effort to work with my teammate							
I was aware of my team							

Enjoyment [9]

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements:

Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I find that participating in the group is enjoyable							
The process of participating in this group is pleasant							
I have fun when I participate in this group							

Exploratory questions related to Social Identity Theory and VR for cooperative multi-user settings

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements:

Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I felt a sense of belonging to my group because s/he or they had the same background like me							
VR helped me to get to know the other better							
I felt a greater sense of belonging to my group in VR than I would have in 2D games							

Do you have any improvement suggestions or want to comment on something for this experiment?

You did it! Good job! Thank you very much for your participation! The experiment is completed. If you have any questions or annotations, please do not hesitate to tell. Please notify the experimenter.